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Population growth and urbanization pattern in Mymensingh district

Tabassum Faria ^{1,*} and Mrs. Nasreen Rafiq ²

¹ Department of Geography and Environment, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Dhaka, Dhaka, Bangladesh

² Professor, Department of Geography and Environment, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Abstract

Urbanization plays an important role in the economy of a country. But the pattern and the process of urbanization in Bangladesh is very much uneven. So, for the economic development of a country, it is necessary to emphasis on the process and pattern of urbanization. That's why for my project work I selected my topic on "Population Growth & Urbanization pattern of Mymensingh District" with the help of my supervisor. From my project paper, it is clearly seen that the pattern of urbanization in Mymensingh district is also very much uneven as like as overall scenario of Bangladesh. Among the 12 upazilas of Mymensingh district, Mymensingh Sadar upazila is well developed with municipal facilities that's why most of the people are concentrated here. On the other hand, Dhobaura upazila is the lowest urbanized area, because of the absence of some common urban facilities. On the other hand, Phulpur upazila ranks 1st position in area measuring scale but has a very low level of urbanization. This study will help to understand the overall scenario of "Population Growth & Urbanization Pattern of Mymensingh District". This analysis will also play in beneficial role to the proper urban management of the Mymensingh district.

Keywords: Urbanization pattern; Population Growth; urban facilities; Inter census urbanization; Mymensingh

1. Introduction

Urbanization generally refers to a process in which an increasing proportion of the world or nation or region's population lived in urban areas. Historically, it has been closely connected with modernization, industrialization, and the sociological process of rationalization. Urbanization is a process that relates to the movement of people from rural to urban areas, with population growth equating to urban migration [1]. According to Carter [2], "The word urban refers to a particular type of place where the economic concentration of non-agricultural activities and the social concentration of particular types of values, behavior, organization, and institutions are present." According to Thompson [3], "Urbanization is characterized by movement of people from small communities concerned solely with agriculture to other larger communities whose activities are primarily centered in government, trade, manufacture, and allied interests." According to Louis Wirth [4], "Urbanization is a way of life." Urbanization is a trend in the increasing proportion of the national population living in urban centers [5]. Urbanization is recognized as one of the most important development phenomena of the contemporary world. It will be even more significant in the future, both as an engine of economic growth and an agent of economic development. However, Bangladesh remains a low-urbanized country compared to other countries, although both the pace of urbanization and the growth of absolute urban population will be remarkably high. On the other hand, the level of urbanization is not evenly distributed throughout the country. Therefore, for proper development of the country, it is necessary to implement effective urban management policies and strategies. The main aim of this study is to probe into the population growth and urbanization pattern of Mymensingh district from 1981 to 2011 [6,10]. The main objective of this project work is to analyze the population

* Corresponding author: Tabassum Faria

growth and urbanization pattern of Mymensingh district and also to understand the past and present population growth as well as upazila-wise urbanization pattern of Mymensingh district and compare it with the national urbanization pattern of the country.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Methods

Methodology is the systematic way of conducting research. Setting appropriate methodology is an integral part of a research. There are various steps to conduct research. This study was conducted by using various secondary data because of time constrain. The main source of data is previous census report & the various report of Bangladesh Bureau of statistics (BBS). Data is presented using MS EXEL and map is created using GIS & ARC Info software.

2.2. Study Area

Mymensingh district is the study area of my project work, because it is located very close to Bangladesh's capital city Dhaka. It is located between 24°15' and 25°12' north latitudes and 90°49' east longitudes. It is bounded by Meghalaya state of India & Garo hills in the north, on the south by Gazipur district, on the east by the districts of Netrokona and Kishoregonj, and on the west by district of Sherpur, Jmalpur and Tangail.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Level of Urbanization in Bangladesh

Level of urbanization in Bangladesh grew at a sluggish rate up to the 60s & later they flourished at a faster rate. Urban population growth rate was extremely high in the 1980s & 1990s, over 7 percent per year annually. It has, however fallen since then but still remains at about 4 percent per year. [7,11]

Figure 1 Level of urbanization in Bangladesh [7,8,10]

From the above graph it is seen that, the level of urbanization of Bangladesh was about 28.39% in the year of 2011 [9]. But this was only about 8.7% during 1974.

3.2. Trend of annual population growth rate and the level of urbanization in Mymensingh district

From the above figure it is seen that, the annual growth rate of the total population is decreasing; on the other hand, the level of urbanization is increasing. According to the preliminary census report of 2011, the annual growth rate is 1.28% & the level of urbanization is about 15.62%. But during the period of 1981 & 1991 the annual growth rate was high than at present time, which was about 1.74% & 2.05%, but the Level of urbanization was very low than the present level, which was about 10.73% & 12.89% respectively. From the census report of 2011, it is seen that among 15.62% of total urban population, Paurashava constitute 8.9% & other Urban area consisting about 4.78%.

Figure 2 Trend of Population Growth Rate and the Level of Urbanization [7,8,10]

3.3. Urban Population Distribution of Mymensingh District

Urban population distribution of Mymensingh districts is very uneven. According to the Preliminary census report of 2011, total population & the number of urban populations both are highest in the Mymensingh sadar upazila. Bhaluka poses the second position of containing urban population. Dhobaura upazila consisted of the lowest number of urban populations. We can easily realize the current distributional pattern of the urban population of Mymensingh district from the following map.

Figure 3 Urban Population Distribution by Upazilas of Mymensingh District [10]

3.4. Urbanization Pattern by Upazilas in Mymensingh District

3.4.1. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Mymensingh Sadar Upazila

The level of Urbanization in this upazila is highest during 2001 & 2011. According to the preliminary census report of 2011 [9], the level of urbanization in this upazila is about 15.26%. On the other hand, in 1981, the level of urbanization in this upazila is about 42.7%. The level of urbanization is high here than the other upazilas of Mymensingh districts, because of well-developed municipal facilities. The number of urban population is increasing day by day in Mymensingh

sadar upazila , because of some well-developed urban facilities. It is the district headquarters of Mymensingh district, that's why most of the administrative institution is concentrated here. On the other hand, it is well connected to the capital city Dhaka, for that reason day by day the rate of urban population is increasing.

Figure 4 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Mymensingh Sadar Upazila [7,8,10]

It is seen that the number of urban populations is increasing highly in this upazila during the period of 2001 & 2011. During 1981-1991, the decadal growth rate is 12.89% & the annual growth rate is about 1.22%. And the period of 1991-2001, the decadal urban growth rate is 2.22% and the annual growth rate about 0.22%.

- **Communication:** The communication facilities of this upazila are good than the other upazilas of Mymensingh district. There are about 100 km pucca road, 45 km. semi pucca road, and 590 km. mud road & 51 km. railways.
- **Factories & Industries:** There are about 1 jute mill, 3 flour mills, 3 ice factories, 1 tannary, 8 engineering workshops, 8 weaving industries are found in this upazila's.
- **Urbanization:** The urban area of Mymensingh Sadar Upazila consists of 1 paurashava & 8 adjoining mauzas, which occupies an area of 68.03 Sq Km. of which 21.7 Sq km is under paurashava. The main urban centre of this upazila is Mymensingh Paurashava.

3.4.2. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Bhaluka Upazila

The level of urbanization in this upazila is increasing rapidly at present time, because of recent development of garments factories & other manufacturing industries. It is also well connected to the Dhaka, that's why the rate of urbanization is increasing. It is seen that the level of urbanization is highest in the year of 2011. According to the preliminary census report of 2011, the level of urbanization in this upazila is about 14.31%. This was only about 4.88% in the year 1981. From the following graph it is also seen that the number of urban populations are increasing highly in this upazila, during 2001 & 2011. During the period of 1981-1991, the decadal growth rate is about 79.71% & the annual growth rate is about 6.04%.

Figure 5 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Bhaluka Upazila [7,8,10]

And the period of 1991-2001, the decadal urban growth rate about 13.8% & the annual growth rate is about 1.30%.

- **Communication Facilities:** There are about 40 km pucca road, 30 km semi pucca road & 113 km mud road & 17 nautical mile waterways (during rainy season) in this upazila.
- **Factories & Industries:** There are some textile mills, ceramic mills, spinning mills are & some fish feed are established in this upazila. There are also found some cottage industries in this upazila-s. Such as 10 welding factories, 40 Goldsmith, 350 tailoring etc.
- **Urbanization:** The Urban area of Bhaluka upazila consists of one paurashava and 3 adjoining mauzas, which altogether occupy an area of 30.03 sq km. Of which 5.10 sq km is under paurashava. The main urban centre of this upazila is BHALUKA paurashava.

3.4.3. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Gaffargaon Upazila:

From the following graph it is seen that, the level of urbanization of Gaffargaon upazila is increasing gradually. According to the census of 1981, the level of urbanization in this upazila was about 6.39%. This is now increasing to a level of 9.90%, according to the preliminary census report of 2011. The reason for that increasing is for improvement of the communication facilities & the establishment of new manufacturing & cottage industries etc. It is seen that the number of urban populations is increasing day by day. According to the preliminary census report of 2011, the number of urban populations in this upazila is about 42,641, which were about 32,997 during the period of 2001.

Figure 6 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Gaffargaon Upazila [7,8,10]

During the period 1981-1991 the decadal growth rate of urban population is about 16, 59% & the annual growth rate is about 1.55%. And the period of 1991-2001, the annual growth rate is about .69%, but the decadal growth rate is about 7.11%.

- **Communication Facilities:** There are about 75 km. pucca road, 5 km semi pucca road, 718 km mud road, 24.75 km railway & 69 nautical mile water ways are found in this upazila.
- **Industries:** There are about 48 flour mills, 58 rice mills 2 oil mills, 10 saw mill, 2 press & 1 soap factory are also located here. There are also located some cottage industries, such as 50 goldsmith, 80 blacksmith, 22 welding, & 500 tailoring.
- **Urbanization:** The urban area of Gaffargaon upazila constitute of Gaffargaon paurashava & adjoining 6 mauzas. But the main urban centre of Gaffargaon upazila is Gaffargaon paurashava.

3.4.4. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Gauripur Upazila

From the following graph, it is seen that the level of urbanization in this upazila is increasing gradually, but the year of 2001, the level of urbanization is decreasing to a level of 0.05%. According to the preliminary census of 2011, the level of urbanization of this upazila is about 7.92%. This was about 6.86% in the year of 1981. It is seen that; the rate of urban population is highest in the year 2011. According to the preliminary census of 2011; the urban population of this upazila is about 25,576. But during the period of 1981 the number of urban populations was only about 14,370. Day by day the number of urban populations is increasing with the improvement of job facilities, health facilities, educational facilities etc.

Figure 7 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Gauripur Upazila[7,8,10]

- **Communication Facilities:** There are about 38 km pucca road, 2 km semi pucca road 564 km mud roads and 20 km railways in this upazila's.
- **Industries:** There are about 1 cotton mill, 19 flour mills, 109 rice mills, 4 ice factories are situated here. There are also found some cottage industries in this upazila's, such as, 30 goldsmith, 200 blacksmith, 6 potteries, 1500 wood work, 25 welding & 2000 tailoring in this upazila.
- **Urbanization:** Gauripur paurashava is the only urban area of this upazia. It consists of 9 wards, 34 mahallahs, which occupies an area of 8.7 sq km.

3.4.5. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Ishwarganj Upazila

From the following graph, it is seen that the level of urbanization is highest in 2001. According to the preliminary census of 2011, the present level of urbanization is about 9.10%. But it was only about 6.75% in the year of 1981. It is also seen that the trend of urban population in Ishwarganj upazila is increasing. According to the census of 2011, the number of urban populations is about 34,231. During 1991-2001, the decadal growth rate of urban population is about 31.47% & the annual growth rate is about 2.77%.

Figure 8 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Ishwarganj Upazila[7,8,10]

- **Communication Facilities:** There are about 24 km pucca roads, 10 km semi pucca road, 555 km mud road in this upazila.
- **Industries:** There are about 63 flour mills, 64 weaving mills, 48 goldsmiths, 62 blacksmith, 60 potteries, 225 woodwork, & 232 tailoring in this upazila.
- **Urbanization:** Ishwarganj Paurashava & 4 adjoining mauzas constitute the urban area of this upazila. The total urban area of this upazila is about 15.82 Sq.km. of which 12.48sq km area consist of Ishwarganj paurashava. The main urban centre of this upazila is Ishwarganj Paurashava.

3.4.6. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Muktagacha Upazila

From the following graph, it is seen that, the level of urbanization is highest in the year of 2011, which is about 12.01%. In 1981, the level of urbanization in this upazila was about 6.34%. At present time, the level of urbanization is increasing, because of some facilities such as, better improvement in communication & health facilities, educational facilities etc. But in the year of 1981, it was only about 6.34%. It is also seen that, the number of urban populations in this upazila is upward sloping. According to the preliminary census of 2011, the number of the total urban population of this upazila is about 49,915. This was only about 16,292 in the year of 1981. During the period 1991-2001, the decadal growth rate of this upazila is about 62.36% & the annual growth rate is about 4.97%.

Figure 9 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Muktagacha Upazila[7,8,10]

- **Communication Facilities:** there are about 38.50 km pucca road, 11 km semi pucca road, & 310 km mud road in Muktagacha upazila.
- **Industries:** There are 15 biscuit factories, 12 oil mills, 3 press, 16 saw mills, 221 rice mills & 2 bidi factory & 12 dairy products (ghee) factory in this upazila.
- **Urbanization:** Muktagacha paurashava is the only urban area of this upazila. According to the census of 2001, it consists of 9 wards, & 21 mahallahs, occupying an area of 11.97 sq km.

3.5. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Nandail Upazila

From the following graph, it is seen that, the level of urbanization is highest in the year of 2011, which is about 10.78%. But in 1981, the level of urbanization was only about 4.28%. The level of urbanization is rapidly increasing during the period of 2001 & 2011, which is about 9.89% and 10.78% respectively. But it was only about 4.28% during the period of 1981. From the following graph, it is also seen that, the number of urban populations is highest in the year of 2011. During the period of 1991 & 2001 the decadal growth rate is highest, which is about 11.87% & the annual growth rate is about 7.75%. But during the period of 1981-1991, the decadal growth rate was about 9.58% & the annual urban growth rate is 0.92%.

Figure 10 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Nandail Upazila[7,8,10]

- **Communication Facilities:** There are about 10.85 km pucca road, 45 km semi pucca road, 400 km mud road & 15.5 km railway in this upazila.
- **Industries:** There are about 54 flour mills, 1 textile mill, 2 weaving factories, 35 goldsmiths, textile mill, 2 weaving factories, 35 goldsmiths, & 35 blacksmiths.
- **Urbanization:** The urban area of Nandail upazila encompasses one paurashava & two adjoining mauzas which altogether occupies an area of 35.44 sq km. But the main urban centre is the Nandail Paurashava.

3.6. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Trishal Upazila

Trishal upazila is one the most recently flourished urbanized area of Mymensingh zilla because of, some educational institution, newly established industries & well connected with Dhaka city. According to the preliminary result of 2011, the level of urbanization in this upazila is about 13.36%. But in 1981, it was only about 9.38%. From the following graph, it is seen that, the number of urban populations is increasing rapidly during 2001 & 2011. According to the preliminary census report of 2011 the number of urban populations is about 56,002. At present time people are getting more urbanized because of some urban facilities.

Figure 11 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Trishal Upazila[7,8,10]

According to the preliminary census of 2011 [9], the number of urban populations is about 56,002 but, in the year of 1981, it was only about 25,152.

- **Communication:** There are about 22.92 km pucca roads, 644 mud road, 16.25 km railway are found in this upazila.
- **Industries:** There are about 37 rice mills, 29 ice factories, 25 saw mill, 1 bidi factory, 78 weaving factories & 65 goldsmith industries are situated in this upazila.
- **Urbanization:** The urban area of Trishal upazila encompasses one paurashava & an adjoining mouza, which altogether occupies an area of 34.83 sq km. But the main urban centre of Trishal upazila is Trishal Paurashava.

3.6.1. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Phulpur Upazila

From the following graph, it is seen that the level of urbanization is increasing. According to the preliminary result of 2011 census the level of urbanization in these upazila is about 4.26%. Although it has a large area, but the level of urbanization is low with comparison to other upazila of Mymensingh district. But at present, with the improvement of communication facilities & other urban facilities the level of urbanization is increasing gradually in this upaila. It is seen that the number of urban Population is increasing day by day. According to the census of 2011, the number of urban Population in this upazila is about 25,628. But it was only about 9,506 during the period of 1981.

Figure 12 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Phulpur Upazila [7,8,10]

During the period 1991-1981 and 2001-1991, the decadal growth rate is about 13.08% and 11.94% respectively.

- **Communication Facilities:** The communication facilities in this upazila are not so good. There are about 33 km of pucca roads, 49 km of semi pucca & 2 km railway in this upazila.
- **Industries:** There are about 76 rice mills, 5 ice cream factory, 5 biscuit factories, 6 weaving, 20 welding, 300 bamboo work & 40 goldsmith factories are found in this upazila.
- **Urbanization:** Phulpur upazila headquarters is the only urban area of this upazila. It consist of 6 mouzas and occupies an area of 8.28 sq km. There are about 16 educational institutions, 4 cinema halls, 5 theater group, 1 clinic / Hospital, 1 library, 1 dakbunglows & 1 post office are situated in Phulpur town or upazila's headquarters of Phulpur upazila.

3.6.2. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Fulbaria Upazila

Figure 13 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Fulbaria Upazila [7,8,10]

From the above graph, it is seen that, the level of urbanization was highest during the year of 2001. But according the preliminary census report of 2011 [9], the level of urbanization is decreasing, from this report it is seen that the level of

urbanization is about 11.28%, which was about 15.80% during 2001. But in 1981 it was only about 7.88%. From the following graph, it is also seen that, the urban population of this upazila is slightly decrease at present time in this upazila. According to the preliminary census report of 2011, the number of urban Population in this upazila is about 50,584, which were about 62,565 in the year 2001.

During the period 1991-1981, the decadal growth rate of this upazila is about 96.32%, & annual growth rate is 6.98%. And during the period of 199-2001, the decadal growth rate is 2.13% & the annual growth rate is 0.21%.

- **Communication Facilities:** There are about 29 km of pucca roads, 38 km semi pucca roads, & 3001 km of mud roads.
- **Industries:** There are about 3 flour mills, 4 ice factories, 6 biscuits factories, 40 welding factories, 45 goldsmith & 3 cocoon production centers.
- **Urbanization:** Fulbaria paurashava & 5 adjoining mouzas of Fulbaria upazila are the urban area of this upazila. The main urban center of this upazila is Fulbaria paurashava.

3.6.3. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Haluaghat Upazila

The level of urbanization is not so good in this upazila. According to the census of 2011, the level of urbanization of this upazila is about 4.04%. In the period of 2001, the level of Urbanization is slightly decreasing with the comparison of 1991. In 1991 the level of urbanization in this upazila was about 4.04% & which was decreasing to 2001 at the level of about 3.92%. It is seen that; the number of urban populations is increasing. According to the preliminary census report of 2011, the urban population of this upazila is about 11,710. Which was only about 6,793 during the census year of 1981.

Figure 14 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population of Haluaghat[7,8,10]

From 1991-1981, the decadal growth rate was 14.90% & the annual growth rate was 1.40%. And in the period 1991 & 2001 the decadal growth rate & the annual growth rate is decreasing to about 2.24% & 0.23%.

- **Communication Facilities:** The communicational facilities are not well furnished in Haluaghat upazila. There are only about 43 km pucca road, 17 km semi pucca road, 350 km mud road & 20 km railway in this upazila.
- **Urbanization:** Haluaghat upazila Headquarters is the only urban area of this upazila. It consists of of about 2 mouzas & occupies an area of 2.7 sq km. There are about 14 educational institutions, 1 vocational training centre, 1 library, 2 cinema hall, 1 dance school & 1 music school are situated in this upazila.

3.6.4. Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Dhobaura Upazila

The level of urbanization is lowest in this upazila in comparison with the other upazilas of Mymensingh district. The communication facilities and the other urban facilities such as, drainage, educational facilities, & health facilities are not so good, that's why the level of urbanization is very poor here. According to the preliminary census report of 2011 [9], the level of urbanization is only about 3.53%. And in 1981, it was only about 1.58%. It is also seen that; the number of urban populations is very low here. The total population is huge, but the number of urban Population in Dhobaura is not large, because of lack of urban facilities. According to the preliminary census result of 2011, the number of urban populations in Dhobaura is about 61,588, but the total population is about 19, 6,284. In 1981 the number of urban populations was only about 1875. But it is positive sign that the number of urban populations is increasing, due to the improvement of some urban facilities.

Figure 15 Level of Urbanization and increase of urban population in Dhobaura Upazila [7,8,10]

- **Communication Facilities:** The communication facilities are not so good in Dhobaura upazila. There are only about 15 km semi pucca road, 350 km of mud road & 22 nautical miles of water ways.
- **Factories & Industries:** The number of factories & industries are also not so high. There are about 3 saw mills, 100 rice mills, 17 goldsmith, 25 potteries, and 2 welding factories in this upazila.
- **Urbanization:** Dhobaura upazila headquarters is the only urban centers of this upazila. It consists of 2 mouzas & occupies an area of 5.595 sq km. There are about 12 educational institutions, 1 cinema hall, 2 public toilets are situated in Dhobaura upazila headquarter.

4. Conclusion

Urbanization is recognized as one of the most important developmental phenomena of the contemporary world. After the liberation war, the urbanization process of Bangladesh is increasing rapidly. But the level of urbanization in Bangladesh is also characterized by a spatially uneven form. From my project work, it is easily seen that, the uneven urbanization patterns are also exist in Mymensingh district.

A brief description of my project findings is given below:

- The urbanization pattern of Mymensingh district is very much uneven as like as overall scenario of Bangladesh.
- Among the 12 upazilas in Mymensingh district, Mymensingh Sadar upazila is the most urbanized area of this district.
- About half of the total urban population is concentrated in Mymensingh Sadar upazila.
- Bhaluka upazila is possess the second position of urbanization in Mymensingh district, but is also far behind of development.
- Dhobaura upazila is the lowest urbanized area because of absence of some common urban facilities.
- On the other hand, Phulpur upazila ranks 1st position in area measuring scale, but has a very low level of urbanization.
- The educational facilities & other urban facilities are mainly concentrated at the Sadar upazila.
- This district has also lack behind some other urban facilities, such as, fire service station, playground, library, health facilities & road network etc.
- Urbanization is a pre-requisite for the economic development of a country. But unplanned urbanization can negatively effect on the economy. That's why it is necessary to take proper action for urban management of the country.

Recommendations

For proper management of the urbanization in Mymensingh district following steps should be taken. Such as: -

- Proper planning is needed for every urban center of Mymensingh district.
- Decentralization of administrative, economic & social investment to a greater extent is necessary at upazila level & paurashava level.

- The following urban facilities should be developed to urban local bodies such as- School, educational institutions, public health, community health centers area, hospitals, traffic management & civic policing activities.
- The functions of the local government should be clearly delineated.
- Proper steps should be taken for sewerage & drainage management.
- Urban local bodies should be given responsibility for solid waste management.
- Measures should be taken for creating self-employment by providing different training of the young unemployed people.
- It is necessary to take proper step for decentralizing the educational & health facilities to the paurashava level.
- The integration of villages with union, paurashava, on upazila level town will be essential.
- Transportation network should be well connected to the whole country.

If above these steps are taken properly, I hope, the urban scenario of Mymensingh district will be improved to a greater extent.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is disclosed.

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